

A WORD FROM

“ESRs will develop new techniques to push the boundaries of knowledge and discover new applications of the often-elusive actinides, the heaviest elements of the periodic table.”

Bruce Marsh
LISA Network Coordinator

Hosted by a consortium of world-leading research groups, laboratories and industrial partners, fifteen Early-Stage Researchers will use and develop state-of-the-art experimental and theoretical techniques to explore the applications of actinide elements and associated technologies, for the scientific community and beyond the laboratory.

They will develop new tools and methods for laser ionization and spectroscopy, and bridge the gap between science, industry and society to push the boundaries of knowledge and discover new applications of the often-elusive actinides, the heaviest elements of the periodic table.

Thomas Cocolios
LISA Training Officer

The LISA Network will train a new generation of engineers and scientists ready to tackle the challenges of tomorrow. Our fifteen Early-Stage Researchers will develop their skills through their participation in cutting-edge research projects performed at leading scientific institutions and state-of-the-art high-tech industries. A blend of network-wide training events, advanced courses at each academic institution, and inter-sectorial secondments will strengthen the links between academic, research and industrial partners, ensuring a comprehensive training that will maximise the employability of the trainees.

We are open to welcoming additional young researchers as affiliates to the network. We will endorse their participation in training events and network activities through our PhD label.

Korbinian Hens, Hubner Photonics (Industrial Partner)

The LISA Network wants to prepare trainees to carry out the transfer of knowledge and ideas into real-world products and services that can tackle challenges shared by academy and industry. In this sense, the purpose of the LISA Network is perfectly aligned with the vision of Hubner Photonics, which is striving to increase the availability of the type of laser-based equipment that contributes to an improved quality of life and a better environment.

Beneficiaries:

Partners:

ACTINIDE RESEARCH

Researching actinides, the heaviest elements

A robotic arm handling one of the ISOLDE/MEDICIS radioisotope production targets.

Producing actinides

There are two current routes to produce short-lived actinides and transactinide elements: the spallation of other very heavy elements, and fusion-based reactions. For the first, LISA will investigate new approaches for the development of actinide ion beams, such as volatile-molecule extraction, followed by laser-induced breakup and resonance ionization at Isotope Separator On-line (ISOL) facilities. The application of expertise held by the LISA consortium in radioactive ion beam production and purification will be crucial in expanding the inventory of ISOL beams in the elusive actinide region of the nuclear chart. For the other, the LISA consortium is active in the use and development of all of the state-of-the-art variations of the fusion-based processes. New approaches will be explored to improve the beam intensity, efficiency, and resolution of the techniques: higher primary beam intensities, ink-jet deposition to produce novel targets, and high-definition gas catcher components.

Developing atomic spectroscopy

With the advent of tuneable lasers, today it is possible to perform high-resolution spectroscopy of atomic structures and identify single energy levels of strongly correlated electrons in the atomic shell. The importance of relativistic effects renders calculations in these systems particularly complex. The state-of-the-art approaches that allow high-level treatment of actinides and superheavy elements are the relativistic-coupled cluster (CC), configuration interaction (CI) approaches, and multi-configuration Dirac-Fock (MCDHF) approaches. The development of the coupled cluster approach (High sector Fock space coupled cluster) within the LISA project will extend the applicability of this method and improve its accuracy by an order of magnitude. Experimentally, higher resolution can be achieved by refining the existing techniques. For example, the study of atomic systems at CERN is possible with resonance ionization spectroscopy performed at the CRIS experiment, while the study of photodetachment of radioactive ion beams of negative ions is possible with the GANDALPH experiment. Within LISA, we will couple GANDALPH and CRIS to create a one-of-a-kind, multi-purpose laser spectroscopy apparatus to bring about the photodetachment measurements of the most exotic actinides within reach.

Peering into atomic orbitals with lasers

Cutting-edge setups explore exotic nuclei

Exploring nuclear structure

The lack of fundamental ground-state nuclear structure data in the actinide region and beyond is a testament to the challenges faced with such isotopes, such as low production rates that require extremely sensitive experimental set-ups.

Innovation within LISA will enable the systematic investigation of the evolution of nuclear structure properties, like spin, charge radii and electromagnetic moments in the heaviest elements: the sensitivity of the charge radii to octupole deformation in the actinide isotopes with mid-shell neutron numbers will be explored and the charge radii measurements of nobelium will be extended to known isomeric states in the region. Such experimental data will support our understanding of super energetic events, such as the recently observed neutron star mergers.

Developing laser technologies

The LISA activities require a range of industrial and scientific laser solutions. Over recent years, groups within the LISA Network have built strong links with the industrial sector and they are at the forefront of establishing the use of high-reliability industrial solid-state lasers for scientific purposes. The consortium will allow researchers and one of our industrial partners (M-Squared Lasers) to jointly develop the pulse-amplified research Ti:Sapphire laser into a commercial-grade product, greatly improving its ease of use and reliability, facilitating its adoption for a vast range of uses beyond the immediate scope of the network. Furthermore, the turnkey 'C-Wave' laser from Hubner Photonics will be adapted to the needs of the laser spectroscopy community with the help of Lioptec, one of the industrial partners. Both of these new laser systems will be characterised and validated with a real-world test at the world's most sensitive collinear laser spectroscopy experiments at the LISA research partner facilities.

CERN will promote these high-tech developments and form the hub of LISA for knowledge transfer.

Lasers measure tiny atomic shifts due to nuclear structure

LISA FOR SOCIETY

The societal impact of LISA will require the group of Early Stage Researchers to apply their understanding of the core topics of the network beyond the realms of fundamental research, namely in nuclear medicine and radioecology; and to share it with the wider community.

MEDICAL

The LISA Network will investigate the production of ²²⁵Ac for medical applications. This isotope has great prospects in the treatment of distributed cancers, the deadliest and most difficult to treat. The supply of ²²⁵Ac currently relies on limited reserves from twentieth-century nuclear stockpiles, which are being de-commissioned and thus inaccessible. By implementing the LISA laser technology at research facilities, high-purity samples of ²²⁵Ac can be delivered for medical research in Europe. The technology will be stringently tested towards the next generation ISOL facilities, where this isotope could be produced in sufficient quantities for patient care.

ENVIRONMENTAL

The actinides are so rare in the environment that their presence is usually a sign of a nuclear incident. Monitoring systems rely on the detection of the tiniest amounts. Moreover, the relative distribution of these actinides is a clear indicator of their origin. The proposed developments with the LISA project will allow the fast simultaneous measurement of all major actinides, which will strongly improve the current time-consuming practice of sequential measurements and help refining the entire monitoring process.

OUTREACH

The members of the LISA Network are committed to public engagement and the dissemination of knowledge to a wider audience to promote a positive image of nuclear research. LISA will build on that experience and share its impact across social media and knowledge dissemination platforms such as Scholarpedia (www.scholarpedia.org), as well as regular events at local high schools, tours of cutting-edge facilities, and events like the laboratories' Open Days or Researchers' Night.

Getting involved

Research associated with the Network at JGU

We value training researchers and sharing our work

PhD Label

For those looking to benefit in greater depth from the LISA network there is the LISA PhD label, open to PhD students who perform research related to the activities of the network. The label is given to researchers who participate in at least three events organised by the Training Office, show mobility and internationalisation in their training and research profile, and contribute to the science communication strategy of the LISA network.

Candidates for the PhD Label may participate in all events under the same conditions as the ESRs, gain access to additional training opportunities proposed within the LISA network, and get support from the LISA Training Office in defining and following up on their training. Moreover, they get to network with all the ESRs, as well as with our Beneficiaries and Partners across Europe and the world.

Training and Education

Researchers interested in the work of LISA can easily get involved by following one of the training events, on themes from actinide production, to nuclear structure, to computational techniques.

TIMELINE

Recent scientific and technical highlights in actinide research

2016

ATOM-AT-A-TIME LASER RESONANCE IONIZATION SPECTROSCOPY OF NOBELIUM

A foray into the unknown atomic structures of transfermium elements: for the first time, ultra-rare Nobelium was studied by laser resonance ionisation. The spectacular sensitivity of the experimental set-up allowed the structure of the outer shells to be probed, defying even the most sophisticated theoretical models.

2017

HIGH-RESOLUTION LASER SPECTROSCOPY OF LONG-LIVED PLUTONIUM ISOTOPES

Low production cross section, nuclear instability, and minimal current knowledge of optical transitions: these massive challenges, often associated with heavy element studies, were overcome with the first collinear laser spectroscopy of Plutonium, the heaviest element thus far studied with this method.

2018

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE SHAPE-STAGGERING EFFECT IN MERCURY NUCLEI

Laser ionisation spectroscopy was used to probe the fascinating region of neutron deficient Mercury, where huge jumps in charge radius are seen when successively removing neutrons from the nucleus. The results, coupled with state-of-the-art Monte Carlo shell model calculations, cut to the heart of the fifty-year-old problem. The nature of the jumps are now understood as a critical phenomenon of a quantum phase transition.

2019

THE LISA NETWORK IS BORN

Ideas were refined, the partner institutes came together, and the word was out for young researchers to join in on exciting developments in the study of actinides.

2020

THE ELECTRON AFFINITY OF ASTATINE

The electron affinity of Astatine was determined using laser photodetachment spectroscopy. Knowledge of this fundamental chemical property now paves the way for its use in Targeted Alpha Treatment of certain cancers, and provides a benchmark for theoretical models, whose output must be refined to match the new observations, revealing the extent to which quantum and relativistic effects play a role in atomic structure. The developed technique opens the door for similar studies on even heavier elements: the actinides.

2020

THE ERA OF LISA ACTINIDE STUDY

The ESRs begin their work on the laser ionisation and spectroscopy of actinides, with the hopes of populating the timeline with more highlights in years to come. These highlights are the beginning of a new chapter in actinide research. They pave the way for a deeper and more complete understanding of the structures of some of the most exotic elements, and the group of LISA ESRs will collaborate to develop sensitive experimental techniques and accurate theoretical models.

ACTINIDES IN NUMBERS

Heavy elements are...

CHANGING SOCIETY

0.05
"mass in micrograms of a radioisotope used for a Targeted Alpha Therapy Treatment"

130000
mass in micrograms of the active molecule used for a chemotherapy treatment

CHANGING WHAT IS POSSIBLE

470 billion
"years would pass before a Thorium nuclear clock would lose a second"

2
Years pass before a quartz clock loses a second

DIFFICULT TO GET HOLD OF

27 million
"cost in USD for one gram of Californium - the second heaviest element that can be produced in a quantity that is visible with the naked eye"

55
The cost in USD of one gram of gold.

Credits & Acknowledgement

LISA

Contributors: Thomas Elias Coccolios, Jake Johnson, Bruce Marsh

Editor: Jake Johnson

Coordination: Isabelle Fontaine

With special thanks to: Early Stage Researchers, Beneficiaries and Partners

CERN

EU Projects Office: Daniela Antonio, EU Communication Officer

Graphic Design Service: Melissa Loyse Perrey, Graphic Designer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 861198.

Find out more about LISA:
lisa-itn.web.cern.ch

SHINING LIGHT ON THE HEAVIEST ELEMENTS

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LISA
Laser Ionisation and Spectroscopy of Actinides